

A Logical Clash With the Prevailing Prejudice in Jagamohan Lala's Play 'Babaji'

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Abstract

Reason and religion is always in conflict since time immemorial. But when this religion becomes the route to regulate false belief and superstition among people this became detrimental for the civilization altogether. And in order to make the contemporaries conscious of all these wrong beliefs, the writer of the play tried to make the audience aware about the reality of this dramatic world. In this chaos the play Babaji by Jagamohan Lala becomes the path breaking and most innovative work that enlightened people of nineteenth century which was filled with the convictions such as superstitious and illusory in nature.

In the play Babaji becomes the first play to question such things through the apt characterization which seems equal to the people prevalent at that time. And this paper would reveal the subject matter and analyse it through the lance of tradition and transition.

Keywords Tradition, Superstition, Religion, Reason, Modernism, Challenge.

Introduction

JagamohanLala is the first playwright in odia language. He is not the first one to publish a play in this era of 19th century but before that the writer Raghunath Parichha has already published his Plays during this time. But in modern content, this play was the first one to do so. He has collected his contents for the writings from his environment, people and society at that time. His primary intention was to reform the social system and public consciousness. He has written many plays such as- BhramaBanjana, Preeti, and OdishaBijaya and so on. Nineteenth century is the era where so many far reaching changes were introduced. Such as - sati, female infanticide, Mariah practice, growth of education. Due to the expansion of British rulling and the growth of western education, the writers of that time specially used to propagate modern thoughts that are pertinent to the audience at that particular time.

According to AllardyceNicoll- drama is a copy of life, mirror of custom and reflection of truth" which is quite relevant to the text 'Babaji' written by Jagamohan Lala. The characterizations of the play has been inspired from the daily life and justified to the most. Each and every character represented are taken from each corner of the society. The promotion of English education has a great impact on the life of these people. Similar to the works of Fakir Mohan Senapati such as- Patent Medicine, SabhyaJamindar, Dakamunis and so on. Where people can the impact of Britishers as well as the impact of English education that is the excessive consumption of alcohol and this can also be seen among the characters presented in the play Babaji, such as- BabuSubalaPatnaik and Yashu Bhattacharya. These are felicitous example of these real life characters. The character PujariAnand Panda's prankish attitude shows the bad manners that were prevalent at that time.

Nineteenth century was filled with superstition, bad manners, prejudices towards each and everything. Since people were innocent and inexperienced, the devious and cunning people by the use of manipulation they used to trick these ignorant souls. This work also represents how the people at that time were lustful and salacious. The incidents that are represented in the play, were taken from the real life incidents because the similar

incidents can be detected in the newspapers at that time and the name of newspaper is 'UtkalDeepika'. This also shows how the people of that time represents the corruption through their activities. And how they are getting imprisonment for their deeds. This piece of art represents there are so many people in spite of their wrong doings no one is there to investigate their characters properly. This is quite evident how the nineteenth century society was filled with evil politics along with wicked characters. They used to trick people for their benefits. And the instances of the same is quite prevalent in newspaper as per the sources.

In the name of religion all this misconceptions were happening at that time. Due to the ignorance, the people belongs to the middle class society were being trapped by the deceivers. Since religion was such a sensitive content, raising voice against this was not that easier. People like Jagamohan Lala and others were the one who initiated such interrogation and elevated their voice against all this affairs. Among others alcoholism, prostitution, superstition were quite common among the middle class families at that time. That are aptly represented in the characters. Castism was also prevalent in the society where the upper caste people used to harass the lower caste for their own benefits. Narratives regarding ghost, evil spirits were quite prevalent at that time. For this reason, the writer has taken characters to justify the essence of the age. The age was confined with blind faith, misfortune, and black magic and so on.

In the play Babaji the protagonist emerged as the mouthpiece of the writer whose primary objective was to reform the society through relevant characters.

Aim of study

This paper would show how the nineteenth century play *Babaji* has a contemporary significance. How it is trying to create a balance in the society by guiding people in the direction to make the people understand regarding superstition and how the tricksters are deceiving the people in the name of religion. This also has a relevance in this modern time. For that reason this book is also regarded a modern text with modern ideas.

Review of Literature

The context of the paper represent is not at all new to the audience, that how people are being deceived by the imposters in the name of religion with the intention of gaining money and fame. Here the book *Babaji* represents, at that time in nineteenth century, people were easily influenced by these people in order to gain more and more material things in their lives. The primary text of that time was 'UtkalDipika' the well-known newspaper, where people used to collect information regarding the contemporary issues.

And accordingly when someone reads the play *Babaji*, it is quite obvious how these people get to know the authenticity of the text. This text also tried to educate the contemporaries, when it was time, where people were not that much educated and falsely guided by these people of power. It was a time where not very educated and they used to think, whatever happens that is only because of these people have blind faith in religion, which are ultimately the deceiver's plan to gain advantages from this.

During this time the author JagamohanLala was the first one to raise voice against this that shows the concern of the author, in order to aware these people against such deceivers. This was a path breaking post by the author. He had taken the initiatives to make these people conscious.

Similar to this work, there was another work that was being written by an odia writer Fakir Mohan Senapati. The name of this work is *Rebati*. This book was also published in the nineteenth century, in order to make the people aware regarding the girl child education. This was the time people used to think educating girl child was something sinful and deadly. If anything bad happens in their lives, the foremost reason behind this is that the girl is getting education. The people over there speculate this girl child education as something unfortunate. But here the author in this story has taken the initiatives to introduce the concept of girl child education in the society which has some contemporary significance not in absolute form rather in such a manner that people think of reading and adding this story to the curriculum of the school and colleges. The play Babaji, also has impacted people of nineteenth century till today's time. This is how the book has covered the idea of tradition to transition and it has a similar impact throughout.

Main Text

Marching Towards Chaos:-

This work of art is not an imaginary one rather it is an initiative that is taken by the playwright Jagamohan Lala and here he tries to illustrate the evil activities such as-

deception by the cunning character, superstitious, prejudiced towards certain things that are precisely depicted in this work. This book was only written for the eradication of such superstitious beliefs from the mind of these contemporaries. Due to the influence of western civilization countless works have been produced.

This subject matter of this play represents the protagonist by the name of Babaji and everything is revolving around the protagonist who is exposed to the superstitious society. When the leading character reaches the residence for the purpose of alms of SubalPatnaik who is drunkard by essence, he was tricked by his servant Pujari Anand Panda. By the application of wickedness he also treated badly and initiated misunderstanding regarding the saint. Which advocates that the saint can make the dead alive.

He reached another house after being disappointed by the first one. In that particular scene as well, one may notice he received nothing from the people present over there. He became disheartened but at the same time he has no arrogance and contempt for anyone. While he was resting near the tree he was rubbed by few robbers. He also dedicated all his belongings to the rubbers without getting any ill feeling for these people. Due to the misunderstandings that has been created by the cunning character Pujari, people started believing that the saint is capable of eliminating all this hindrances and depressions of the lives of these people. So what they did, they started approaching the saint for each and everything. But as a leading character he tried his best to make the people aware about the fraudulent that are prevalent in day to day life. They must be aware about all this.

There are two characters such as- James and Shiva mantra. They have come to meet the saint in order to get rid of their grief and unhappiness. Since they have been informed about mystical qualities of the saint. But these mystical qualities are the products of deception and dishonesty which was cleared by the saint. He also tried to make these people understand how the cunning people are taking the advantages of their ignorance in these matters by deceiving them with the presence of shadow and spirits.

When the saint met the scornful character 'pujari' and asked why did he propagated all this myths regarding the saint, he admitted that out of contempt and anger he did it. And when the character Pujari disclosed his real identity that how he deceives people by presenting himself as a protector of these people from the evil spirits. After this the saint made the character realised about the bad deeds and that he is committing crime by deceiving these innocent people and the end result of this disloyalty. He also clarified that by the means of honesty and morality one may live a happy life. These moral lessons needs to be implemented in our life. This is precisely what the subject matter all about.

Tradition and Transition:-

The play Babaji is precisely a work that represents the context of tradition and transition and this transition is not backward but forward. Since we have already discussed how the nineteenth century society is and the attitude of people over there. The playwright has represented the protagonist as the spokesperson of that particular time on what should be done and what should not be done. People must be aware of the superstitious, deceptions that are prevalent in the society. He tried his best to let the people know the reality of these tricksters.

Since this shows the transition towards modernity, the writer Jagamohan Lala was the first playwright to add such contents in this work. It was the time full of misconceptions and myths. People were being deceived due to their simplicity. The primary purpose of this text is to educate these people about the superstition and misconceptions regarding the surroundings and life altogether. And in order to make it rich small events have been adjoined with the main plot to make it a huge success.

Similar to the other structure plays, the playwright has not divided the plot into acts or scene but in the content one may clearly define the events into different acts and sections. Similar to the other plays the subject matter shows there is beginning, middle and end. The beginning of the first resident where the character Pujari is disclosing his real identity and denouement would be the point where the wicked character Pujari is going through the process of realisation and marching towards salvation. The leading character here not only showing correct path to the sinful character Pujari but several other characters to lead a happy and logical life in their lives. When the society was surrounded with such myths, superstition, and misunderstanding and at this moment the playwright Jagamohan Lala is emerging as activist, who is communicating the social challenges to the audience over there.

Conclusion

From the above discussion we perceived that how JagamohanLala's play Babaji is celebrated a play with the content of logicality and modernity. But the point is what modernity is? Getting away from your own culture and tradition is modernity or being logical or rational about each and everything is modernity.

Due to the impact of western civilization, people started behaving religion as a synonyms to superstition. But in reality it is not. Because we may find there are so many rituals in our religion, there are deep notions behind it and that only can be proved by the perspective of science. And religion is not superstition but when superstition comes, it comes through the way of religion since we feel there is no place for the reason in religion. But people need to be logical and aware about the superficiality.

In the Victorian era there was the term 'Victorian compromise ' which suggests one should choose the middle path which suggests one must not be extremely religious or empiricist rather one should follow a balanced life to live peacefully.

This is what the leading character Babaji is presenting in this play. When he made these characters realised their own deeds and ask them to follow the path of honesty and integrity to lead a better life. And this is not the absence of religion or reason but presence of both.

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